

*f*NIRS during movement production: Advances and applications

9–10 June, 2026

Eurasport
Lille, France

Book of Abstracts

UR&PSSS — ULR 7369
Université du Littoral Côte d'Opale
Université de Lille
Université d'Artois

Contents

Forewords	vii
Organisers	vii
Scientific Committee	vii
Industrial Partners	viii
Conference Venue	ix
Keynotes	1
Building <i>f</i> NIRS for the real world: From methodological rigor to real-world neuroscience (<i>Meryem A. Yücel</i>)	1
Mapping the moving mind: Navigating <i>f</i> NIRS applications and artifacts in ecological settings (<i>Luca Pollonini</i>)	2
Oral Sessions	5
Examining cognitive activity associated with bicycle balance (<i>Francois May, Laura Dubuis, Antoine Muller, Thomas Robert, and Maud Ranchet</i>)	5
Cerebral oxygenation and psychophysical responses to auditory stimuli during exhaustive cycle ergometer exercise (<i>Ségolène M. R. Guérin, Costas I. Karageorghis, Marine R. Coeugnet, Marcelo Bigliassi, and Yvonne N. Delevoye-Turrell</i>)	6
Effect of traffic separation and nature integration on affect and cerebral oxygenation during active transport: An immersive virtual reality and multi-study design (<i>Layan Fessler, Ségolène M. R. Guérin, and Yvonne N. Delevoye-Turrell</i>)	7
Neural bases of social audio-motor synchronization: An <i>f</i> NIRS investigation of motor and socio-cognitive networks (<i>Yanis Zaoui, Ugo Place, Thomas Vincent, Louis Bherer, Damien Vitiello, and Valentin Bégel</i>)	8
Initial signal-level validation of a low-cost multimodal <i>f</i> NIRS headband with integrated IMU and PPG (<i>Khadija Khan, Joan Lambert Cause, and Johan Stiens</i>)	9
Effect of age or Parkinson’s Disease on prefrontal activity and walking performance (<i>Maud Ranchet, Isabelle Hoang, Romain Derollepot, Jacques Luauté, Maxime Cheminon, Teodor Danaila, and Laurence Paire-Ficout</i>)	10
Grasping the brain: Neural correlates of grasping performance in 3 to 9 months old preterm infants measured with <i>f</i> NIRS (<i>Nele De Bruyn, Pieter Van den Berghe, Jolien Lamers, Christine Van den Broeck, and Nathalie De Beukelaer</i>)	11

A case study of bilateral grasping development in a single typical developing infant from 3 to 9 months (<i>Nele De Bruyn, Pieter Van den Berghe, Jolien Lamers, Christine Van den Broeck, and Nathalie De Beukelaer</i>)	12
How many trials are enough? An <i>f</i> NIRS study of real and illusory movement (<i>Brieuc Léger, Ophélie Pila, Christophe Duret, Arthus Peltais, Julien Bonnal, and Stéphane Perrey</i>)	13
Development and evaluation of a multimodal EEG- <i>f</i> NIRS neurofeedback platform for motor imagery (<i>Camille Muller, Isabelle Corouge, Thomas Prampart, Elise Bannier, and Pierre Maurel</i>)	14
Poster Session	15
Vasoreactivity of the prefrontal cortex during exercise in men living with type 1 diabetes following a single dose of cocoa flavanols (<i>Elodie Lespagnol, Costantino Balestra, Julie Dereumetz, Cassandra Parent, Julien Boissière, Sémah Tagougui, Clément Leveque, Michel P. Hermans, Martin Feelisch, Patrice Maboudou, Farid Zerimech, Romain Meeusen, Cajsa Tonoli, Danusa D. Soares, and Elsa Heyman</i>)	15
User acceptability and ergonomic evaluation of a portable <i>f</i> NIRS avatar during ecological motor activities (<i>Valentin Cretaine, Alice Martinez, Morgane Pinot, Ségolène M. R. Guérin, and Jean-Dominique Guérin</i>)	17
Exploring the effects of body position on neurobiological, behavioral and psychophysiological dynamics (<i>Paul Butin, Layan Fessler, and Cédric T. Bonnet</i>)	18
Cortical activation during robot-based sensory processing in stroke and healthy controls: A pilot <i>f</i> NIRS study (<i>Siqi Yang, Charlotte Heremans, Inês Martins, Jolien Gooijers, Jean-Jacques Orban de Xivry, and Geert Verheyden</i>)	19
Multimodal <i>f</i> NIRS-EEG recording during standing cognitive tasks in an immersive olfactory dome (<i>Marine R. Coeugnet, Zeynep Yenigun, Thomas Fontaine, Yvonne N. Delevoye-Turrell, and Marion A. Vincent</i>)	20
Improving <i>f</i> NIRS neuroimaging data analysis during motor paradigms by integrating systemic physiological signals (<i>Salomé L. Delbecq, Pierre Morel, Hadi Abou Nader, and Ségolène M. R. Guérin</i>)	21
Effects of movement tempo on prefrontal cortical activation during short-term sensorimotor synchronization practice (<i>Hadi Abou Nader, Pierre Morel, Salomé L. Delbecq, and Ségolène M. R. Guérin</i>)	22
Keywords Index	25
Author Index	27

Forewords

This two-day event focused on recent advances in the recording of brain activity using *f*NIRS during movement-related tasks (e.g., finger tapping, speech production, cycling, social interactions). The conference addressed current methodological challenges in the field – particularly those related to physiological contamination and multimodal approaches – as well as the latest developments indented to overcome them. Finally, the event aimed to encourage collaboration between researchers from complementary disciplines (e.g., neurosciences, psychology and sports sciences).

Organisers

- Ségolène M. R. Guérin – Associate Professor (ULCO, URePSSS)
- Valentin Dallery-Blet – PhD student (ULCO, URePSSS)
- Léa Mekkaoui – Associate Professor (ULille, URePSSS)

Scientific Committee

Ségolène M. R. Guérin Ségolène Guérin is an Associate Professor of Psychology at the Université du Littoral Côte d’Opale (URePSSS). Her research focuses on the neurocognitive mechanisms underlying the temporal control of motor behaviour and the dynamics of cerebral oxygenation during physical exertion. Grounded in cognitive neuroscience, her work bridges cognitive psychology and movement sciences, with particular expertise in *f*NIRS and frequency-tagging EEG methodologies.

Patrick Mucci Patrick Mucci is Professor in Exercise Physiology at the University of Lille (URePSSS). His research focuses on the limitations of respiratory system during exercise. He is interested in the mechanisms that limit oxygen supply and utilization during exercise in healthy populations (children, adults and seniors) and those with chronic diseases. In this research topic, he studied tissue oxygenation (muscles and prefrontal cortex) during exercise using near-infrared spectroscopy.

Nounagnon F. Agbangla Nounagnon Agbangla is an Associate Professor in Movement Science at the University of Artois (URePSSS). His research focuses on the field of aging, with a particular interest in identifying the factors that contribute to healthy aging. A major component of his investigations concerns the influence of

physical exercise on executive functions in older adults, as well as the exploration of the neurophysiological mechanisms underlying these effects through the use of *f*NIRS.

Industrial Partners

GAZE INTELLIGENCE

Gaze Intelligence Gaze Intelligence supports neuroscience research laboratories in France, Spain, and Portugal with advanced neurophysiological technologies, including *f*NIRS, high-density EEG, and multimodal integration solutions. The company collaborates closely with academic and clinical teams to enable robust and innovative experimental designs, particularly in mobile and movement-based neuroscience research.

Seenel Imaging Seenel Imaging, a spin-off from INSERM and CHU Amiens-Picardie, is transforming brain exploration with its multimodal Brain Body platform. This unique solution natively integrates high-density *f*NIRS and EEG, hardware-synchronised with the full range of physiological measurements from BIOPAC Systems (ECG, respiration, EDA) within the AcqKnowledge® software environment. Thanks to its patented exoskeleton design, which provides direct access to the scalp, it overcomes hair-related constraints to deliver optimal spatial precision and signal quality. A unified interface offering a comprehensive “Brain–Body” perspective, it has been developed to simplify the most demanding multimodal research and to support portability in real-world settings.

Trinoma Trinoma is a company bringing together scientists and engineers specialising in the capture and analysis of movement and its determinants (neurological, biomechanical, etc.). It supports clients from a wide range of sectors – including industry, sport, healthcare and research – in the design and implementation of measurement, data acquisition and data processing solutions.

Conference Venue

Eurasport is a University of Lille platform that enables the conduct of translational research in the field of interactions between physical activity, sport, and health within a single integrated facility. Within this platform, researchers and socio-economic stakeholders benefit from:

- the scientific and methodological expertise of staff from the Unité de Recherche Pluridisciplinaire Sport, Santé, Société (URePSSS);
- an exercise physiology laboratory enabling functional, cardiovascular, respiratory, and muscular assessments during exercise;
- a biology laboratory dedicated to the analysis of blood and muscle tissue samples;
- physical activity facilities (gymnasium, rehabilitation room, and “zen” room) for the implementation of both cross-sectional and longitudinal studies;
- dedicated training spaces.

Research conducted at Eurasport involves healthy individuals, patients with medical conditions, and athletes. As an authorised biomedical research facility, Eurasport is able to host clinical trials involving human participants. The platform hosts the Unité de Recherche Pluridisciplinaire Sport, Santé, Société (URePSSS; ULR 7369), which can support research projects through complementary expertise, particularly in cellular and molecular physiology analyses. Eurasport also hosts the sports medicine department of the Centre Hospitalier Universitaire de Lille.

Keynotes

Building *f*NIRS for the real world: From methodological rigor to real-world neuroscience

Meryem A. Yücel
Boston University, USA

9 June
9:00am
SF1

Biography

Dr. Meryem Ayşe Yücel is a Research Associate Professor in Biomedical Engineering and Technical Director of the Neurophotonics Center at Boston University. She is widely recognized for her contributions to functional near-infrared spectroscopy, particularly in advancing signal processing methods, analytical rigor, and best practices that strengthen methodological standards and inclusivity in neuroimaging. Her work bridges foundational methodological advances with cognitive, clinical, and real-world neuroscience applications, with a strong emphasis on open science and community-driven efforts within the Society for *f*NIRS. She also serves in editorial and leadership roles across the neurophotonics community.

Abstract

*f*NIRS holds real promise for studying the brain beyond the lab, but only if measurements are reliable, reproducible, and work across diverse participants. This keynote presents recent methodological work examining how analysis pipeline choices affect reproducibility, and how participant characteristics such as hair type and skin tone shape signal quality and data inclusivity. We will also briefly discuss recent naturalistic studies from our group at Boston University as examples of *f*NIRS research in the everyday world. Together, this body of work points toward a version of *f*NIRS research that is more rigorous, more inclusive, and better suited to capturing brain function as it unfolds in the real world.

10 June
9:30am
SF1

Mapping the moving mind: Navigating *f*NIRS applications and artifacts in ecological settings

Luca Pollonini

Boston University, USA

Biography

Luca Pollonini is an Associate Professor and Associate Chair of the Department of Engineering Technology at the University of Houston, where he directs the Optical Bioimaging Lab. He earned his master's degree in Electrical Engineering (2000) and Ph.D. in Information Engineering (2004) at the University of Brescia (Italy). In 2022, he was awarded a U.S. Fulbright Scholarship and was elected a Senior Member of the National Academy of Inventors. His primary area of research is optical neuroimaging using functional near-infrared spectroscopy (*f*NIRS), where he contributes to the development of novel instruments, analytical methods, and scientific and clinical applications. His research has been funded primarily by the NIH and NSF, and he has published 40 journal articles and holds 6 patents. He is also an active member of the Society for functional Near Infrared Spectroscopy, where he serves on the Board of Directors and chairs the Communications Committee.

Abstract

Functional Near-Infrared Spectroscopy (*f*NIRS) has become an indispensable methodology across fields ranging from exercise physiology and neurodevelopment to neurorehabilitation and motor neuroscience across the lifespan, enabling non-invasive and real-time brain imaging on the unconstrained body. Its portability makes it the premier tool, alongside electroencephalography (EEG), for mapping cortical activation during dynamic, real-world behaviors – from high-exertion athletic performance and pediatric play to ambulatory navigation, fine motor skills and gait training. By allowing researchers to study the brain while it controls the body and interacts with the environment, *f*NIRS provides a unique window into the neural mechanisms of motor planning, execution, and adaptation in naturalistic settings. In addition, by integrating *f*NIRS into multimodal setups – incorporating peripheral biosensors (ECG, EMG), muscle NIRS (mNIRS), kinematic tracking, and behavioral metrics – researchers can capture a holistic, multi-system view of the relationship between cognitive performance, environmental stimuli, and movement.

The very design of these naturalistic paradigms, while transformative, introduces a fundamental vulnerability to optical imaging. From intense physical exertion to subtle motor activity, movement inevitably induces severe motion artifacts, superficial blood flow changes, and optode-to-skin decoupling. Crucially, because these artifacts are often inherently time-locked to the exercise workload or experimental stimuli, they pose a high risk of being falsely interpreted as genuine physiological or cortical responses. Despite the proliferation of advanced hardware and analytical algorithms,

there is no universal “cure” that perfectly separates true metabolic and hemodynamic signals from movement-induced noise.

This talk will underscore the immense utility of *f*NIRS across these broad domains of science while issuing a critical, constructive warning regarding data fragility. Drawing on objective, data-driven quality assessment frameworks, we will discuss practical, transparent strategies for navigating this noisy landscape. Rather than promising a magic computational fix, the presentation will focus on rigorous methodology – such as objective quality control, signal filtering and multimodal regression techniques – to determine when data can be reliably interpreted. Ultimately, this talk aims to equip researchers with the balance of optimism and skepticism required to ensure reproducible findings when studying the brain in the dynamic environments of human movement and real-world interaction.

Oral Sessions

Examining cognitive activity associated with bicycle balance

9 June
10:30am
SF1

Francois May^{1*}, Laura Dubuis¹, Antoine Muller¹, Thomas Robert¹,
and Maud Ranchet²

¹Univ Eiffel, Univ Lyon 1, LBMC UMR.T 9406, F-69622 Lyon, France

²LESCOT, Univ Gustave Eiffel, Univ Lyon, F-69675 Lyon, France

Background and Objective: Balancing a bicycle is a really complex problem, still not well understood. Lots of studies focused on studying bicycle balance from a mechanical point of view, but mental workload was demonstrated as an important factor for bicycle riding. Still, no objective quantification of the brain activity associated with bicycle balance was made. This study aims to observe the cognitive activity while bicycle riding, in order to assess the automaticity of the riding task.

Methods: 23 participants were asked to pedal under two conditions: *pedaling* on a stationary bike and *riding* a bicycle on a circular path. These two conditions were chosen because the primary difference between them was the control of balance. The brain activity of the prefrontal cortex (HbO₂ and HbR) was recorded using a 20-channel *f*NIRS system during both conditions. 8 short-channel were used for movement artifact correction.

Results: HbO₂ and HbR courses demonstrated a typical haemodynamic response function for the *riding* condition, which was not the case for the *pedaling* condition. Participants showed greater prefrontal cortex activity while riding a bicycle compared to pedaling on a stationary bike.

Conclusion: The increased prefrontal cortex activity for the *riding* condition compared to the *pedaling* demonstrated that the control of balance while riding a bicycle (primary difference between the two conditions) was not a fully automated process. Finally, this study presents encouraging results for further studies about quantifying the mental workload during bicycle balance in multiple situations.

Keywords: bicycle riding, prefrontal cortex, automatic process, movement artifact, stationary bike

Cerebral oxygenation and psychophysical responses to auditory stimuli during exhaustive cycle ergometer exercise

Ségolène M. R. Guérin^{1*}, Costas I. Karageorghis², Marine R. Coeugnet³,
Marcelo Bigliassi⁴, and Yvonne N. Delevoye-Turrell^{3,5}

¹Univ. Littoral Côte d'Opale, Univ. Artois, Univ. Lille, ULR 7369 - URePSSS - Unité de Recherche Pluridisciplinaire Sport Santé Société, F-59140 Dunkerque, France

²Brunel University of London, Uxbridge, Middlesex, United Kingdom

³Univ. Lille, CNRS, UMR 9193 - SCALab - Sciences Cognitives et Sciences Affectives, F-59000 Lille, France

⁴Florida International University, Miami, USA

⁵Institut Universitaire de France (IUF)

Background and Objective: Asynchronous music has often been used to reduce perceived exertion and render the exercise experience more pleasant. Previous research indicates that in-task asynchronous music can reallocate an individual's attentional focus towards task-unrelated signals and increase the use of dissociative thoughts. Nonetheless, the brain mechanisms that underlie the benefits of music during exercise remain largely unknown. The purpose of this registered report was to determine the onset of cerebral oxygenation decline during exercise, and how this is influenced by the presence of motivational asynchronous music.

Methods: *f*NIRS was used to record the prefrontal, motor, parietal and occipital haemodynamic responses of 36 participants ($M_{age} = 23.1 \pm 3.3$ years) who completed a cycle ergometry exercise protocol, starting at 5% above the first ventilatory threshold (VT1), and ending with volitional exhaustion. The task was executed under three conditions on separate sessions: asynchronous music, audiobook control and no-audio control.

Results: Across behavioural and subjective measures – including core affect, perceived exertion and exercise enjoyment – no statistically reliable effects of asynchronous music were observed ($p > .002$), although some non-significant trends were consistent with theoretical propositions. The negative control hypothesis was, however, supported: haemodynamic responses in the occipital cortex did not differ across conditions, thereby verifying the specificity and integrity of the *f*NIRS measurements.

Conclusion: Taken collectively, the present findings highlight the complexities of measuring the effects of music on exercise-related brain activity. Further research employing more homogeneous samples and alternative exercise protocols (e.g., incremental) is warranted to elucidate the neurophysiological mechanisms that underlie the effects of asynchronous music during exhaustive exercise.

Keywords: cerebral oximetry, cycling, physical activity, prefrontal activity, ventilatory threshold

Effect of traffic separation and nature integration on affect and cerebral oxygenation during active transport: An immersive virtual reality and multi-study design

9 June
11:30am
SF1

Layan Fessler^{1*}, Ségolène M. R. Guérin², and Yvonne N. Delevoye-Turrell^{1,3}

¹Univ. Lille, CNRS, UMR 9193 - SCALab - Sciences Cognitives et Sciences Affectives, F-59000 Lille, France

²Univ. Littoral Côte d'Opale, Univ. Artois, Univ. Lille, ULR 7369 - URePSSS - Unité de Recherche Pluridisciplinaire Sport Santé Société, F-59140 Dunkerque, France

³Institut Universitaire de France (IUF)

Background and Objective: Increasing active transport is key to reducing human driven greenhouse gas emissions and improving health outcomes. To facilitate the transition from private cars to active transport, it is crucial to create urban environments that induce positive experiences, fostering positive affective memories and increasing the intention to use these modes in the future. This programmatic registered report aims to investigate whether integrating traffic separation and nature integration into urban concrete environments during active transport sessions (i.e., cycling [Study 1] or walking [Study 2]) would improve the affective experience and reduce cognitive effort.

Methods: Thirty-six adults will participate in three 15-min, moderate-intensity cycling ($n = 18$, Study 1) or walking ($n = 18$, Study 2) sessions involving three different virtual environments: an urban environment (a) without traffic separation; (b) with traffic separation; and (c) with traffic separation and natural features. Affective valence will be measured six times during each session using self-report questionnaires. To assess the neural mechanisms underlying cognitive effort, oxygenation of the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex will be monitored using functional near-infrared spectroscopy throughout the sessions. Remembered pleasure will be measured after each session, using self-reported questionnaires.

Results: Pilot data ($n = 9$) indicated that the protocol was considered to be acceptable ($M = 5.74 \pm 1.30$ out of 9), with low-to-moderate cybersickness reported ($M = 33.92\% \pm 19.64$).

Conclusion: The findings are expected to advance the theoretical understanding of how environmental influences impact affective variables and prefrontal activation. This experimental research will pave the way for future empirical studies examining how urban design can facilitate the transition to active transport.

Keywords: affect, cerebral oximetry, effort, fNIRS, physical activity

9 June
1:00pm
SF1

Neural bases of social audio-motor synchronization: An *f*NIRS investigation of motor and socio-cognitive networks

Yanis Zaoui^{1,2*}, Ugo Place¹, Thomas Vincent³, Louis Bherer^{3,4}, Damien Vitiello¹, and Valentin Bégel¹

¹Université Paris Cité, Institut des Sciences du Sport-Santé de Paris (URP3625), Paris, France

²NaturalPad, Montpellier, France Recherche Pluridisciplinaire Sport Santé Société, F-59140 Dunkerque, France

³Centre EPIC de l'Institut de Cardiologie de Montréal, Montréal, Canada

⁴Département de médecine, Université de Montréal, Montréal, Canada

Background and Objective: Sensorimotor synchronization (SMS) to auditory rhythms relies on the coupling between auditory and motor brain areas. SMS skills are also thought to be rooted in interpersonal interactions and to support social bonding. However, the neurophysiological mechanisms underlying interactive SMS remain poorly understood. This study investigates how a virtual partner's social presence modulates the brain's audio-motor and socio-cognitive networks during movement production.

Methods: We are currently recruiting 80 participants (40 young adults aged 18-35; 40 older adults aged 65-85). Participants tap on a drum pad in synchronization with auditory rhythmic sequences with or without a virtual partner. The degree of socio-communicative interaction will vary across four conditions: interactive (with facial features), intermediate (without facial features), non-interactive (virtual drumsticks only), and auditory control (no virtual partner). Cortical hemodynamics in motor (M1, SMA, PMd) and frontal (mPFC, rTPJ) regions, known to be recruited during both action planning and socio-cognitive processing, are recorded using *f*NIRS (Δ HbO). Tapping asynchrony and variability as well as heart rate variability (HRV) are measured in each condition.

Results: Data collection is currently ongoing. We hypothesize that the interactive condition will elicit lower tapping asynchrony and reduced temporal variability. *f*NIRS data should reveal significantly increasing activation (Δ HbO) in both motor planning regions and frontal areas as the level of socio-communicative interaction increases.

Conclusion: This ongoing study addresses key questions on the behavioral and neurophysiological dynamics of interactive SMS by manipulating the degree of socio-communicative interaction. The findings may highlight how social context enhances audio- motor coordination, offering insights for future rhythm-based motor rehabilitation strategies.

Keywords: sensorimotor synchronization, social cognition, *f*NIRS, virtual reality, motor control

Initial signal-level validation of a low-cost multimodal *f*NIRS headband with integrated IMU and PPG

9 June
1:30pm
SF1

Khadija Khan^{1*}, Joan Lambert Cause¹, and Johan Stiens¹

¹Electronics and Informatics Department, Vrije Universiteit Brussel, Brussels, Belgium

Background and Objective: Functional near-infrared spectroscopy (*f*NIRS) is increasingly used for brain monitoring in naturalistic and mobile environments, but recordings are often affected by motion artefacts, superficial physiological activity, and systemic cardiovascular fluctuations. These challenges highlight the need for multimodal systems, recording *f*NIRS with physiological and motion signals. To address this need, we developed and evaluated a low-cost multimodal *f*NIRS headband integrating inertial measurement unit (IMU) and photoplethysmography (PPG) sensors, and investigated its ability to detect task-locked prefrontal hemodynamic responses using a cognitive-motor task as an initial validation step.

Methods: Pilot data was acquired from one participant performing a 16-block *n*-back task, a cognitive paradigm incorporating a manual button-press motor response on every trial. The system integrates four wavelengths (740, 770, 810, and 850 nm) and four source-detector separations (7.5–35 mm), alongside IMU and PPG. A processing pipeline was implemented from raw light intensity to hemoglobin concentration changes, including signal quality assessment, IMU-based motion screening, bandpass filtering, and short-separation regression. PPG was further evaluated as a physiological nuisance regressor in a task-versus-rest general linear model (GLM).

Results: Signal quality was usable in 8/12 long channels ($\text{SNR} \geq 30$ dB, $\text{SCI} \geq 0.7$), while the 35 mm separation suggested a hardware sensitivity limitation. Task-locked block averaging showed an HbO increase peaking approximately 8–10 s after task onset. Preliminary GLM analysis yielded positive HbO task coefficients across long channels (+0.011 to +0.030 μM), with PPG nuisance regression consistently improving contrast-to-noise ratio.

Conclusion: These findings support the feasibility of the multimodal *f*NIRS headband and pipeline for detecting task-locked prefrontal haemodynamic responses, with validation against a commercial system and extension to dedicated motor task protocols planned as next steps.

Keywords: functional near-infrared spectroscopy, multimodal sensing, physiological noise, short-separation regression, wearable neurotechnology

Effect of age or Parkinson's Disease on prefrontal activity and walking performance

9 June
2:00pm

SF1 Maud Ranchet^{1*}, Isabelle Hoang², Romain Derollepot³, Jacques Luauté^{4,5,6}, Maxime Cheminon⁴, Teodor Danaila⁴, and Laurence Paire-Ficout¹

¹Univ Gustave Eiffel, Univ Lyon, LESCOT, F-69675 Lyon, France

²Ergocentre, France

³Univ Gustave Eiffel, ENTPE, EMob-Lab, 69675 Lyon, France

⁴Service de Médecine Physique et de Réadaptation Neurologique, Hôpital Henry-Gabrielle, Hospices Civils de Lyon, Lyon, France

⁵Inserm UMR-S 1028, CNRS UMR 529, ImpAct, Center de Recherche en Neurosciences de Lyon, Université Lyon-1, Bron, France

⁶Université de Lyon, Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, Lyon, France

Background and Objective: Aging and Parkinson's Disease (PD) affect both motor and cognitive functions, leading to impairments in walking. Physical exercise has been shown to improve walking performance in both populations. However, among the factors associated with walking impairment, neurophysiological mechanisms have been less extensively studied. Therefore, this work summarizes findings from studies examining (1) the effect of aging and PD on prefrontal activity during walking and (2) the impact of an intensive physical exercise-based training program on prefrontal activity during usual walking in PD individuals.

Methods: Ninety-three individuals were divided in 4 groups: 25 younger adults, 25 younger-old adults, 25 older-old adults, and 14 PD adults. They all performed walking tasks including usual walking. Cortical activity in prefrontal cortex, assessed by changes in oxy-hemoglobin (ΔHbO_2) and deoxy-hemoglobin (ΔHbR), was measured using functional near-infrared spectroscopy. Gait performance was recorded using wearable sensors.

Results: During usual walking, prefrontal activity increased with aging and increased further in PD. The increased prefrontal activity is already present in our group of younger-old adults (mean age: 62 ± 4 years-old). Our pilot study also showed that the training program reduced prefrontal activity during usual walking in 14 PD patients.

Conclusion: Our findings suggest that walking requires more cognitive resources, early in aging. The training program reduced prefrontal activity during usual walking in PD patients, suggesting a potential increase in gait automaticity. An on-going study investigate the mid-term effect (at 6 months) of this training program on multiple cortical regions during walking in PD individuals.

Keywords: aging, Parkinson's Disease, cortical activity, walking, physical exercise

Grasping the brain: Neural correlates of grasping performance in 3 to 9 months old preterm infants measured with *f*NIRS

Nele De Bruyn^{1*}, Pieter Van den Berghe¹, Jolien Lamers¹,
Christine Van den Broeck¹, and Nathalie De Beukelaer¹

¹Department Rehabilitation Sciences, Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium

9 June
4:00pm
SF1

Background and Objective: Early upper limb movements are well characterized at the behavioural level, yet their neural correlates remain insufficiently understood particularly in preterm infants.

Methods: We conducted a cross-sectional study including 9 preterm infants (< 36 weeks gestational age) aged 3.5–8 months corrected age who were matched to a group of term-born infants based on corrected age and to another group based on performance using the Hand Assessment for Infants (HAI). An event-related paradigm was used to elicit bilateral grasping and exploration. *f*NIRS data were acquired using 8×8 blunt-tipped optodes positioned over the primary sensorimotor cortex. Trials lasted ~15 s with ~10 s rest. Data were preprocessed using motion correction (TDDR), subject-level GLM (AR-IRLS) and group-level independent t-tests adapted for infant data.

Results: Overall sensorimotor cortical activation increased from 3 to 6 months followed by a decrease until 9 months. At channel level ($q < 0.05$), significant increases were observed in the left hemisphere (C5–C3; FC5–C5; C3–CP3; FC5–FC3). In the right hemisphere, both increases (FC4–C4; FC4–FC6; FC6–C6) and decreases (C2–C4; C4–C6) were identified.

Conclusion: Data from this longitudinal case suggest sensorimotor activity mirrors behavioral performance with a peak around 6 months of age and a decrease afterwards reflecting emerging neural efficiency and skill refinement. Although based on a single child only, these findings provide an important exploratory step toward a better understanding of early neural mechanisms of hand function and may contribute to earlier identification of upper limb impairments in infants at risk for unilateral cerebral palsy.

Keywords: early movement maturation, upper limb, typical developing, brain maturation, infants

9 June
4:30pm
SF1

A case study of bilateral grasping development in a single typical developing infant from 3 to 9 months

Nele De Bruyn^{1*}, Pieter Van den Berghe¹, Jolien Lamers¹,
Christine Van den Broeck¹, and Nathalie De Beukelaer¹

¹Department Rehabilitation Sciences, Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium

Background and Objective: Skill development of early upper limb movements is well characterized at the behavioural level, yet their neural correlates remain insufficiently understood.

Methods: We measured one typical developing male child (birthweight 4080 g; gestational age: 40 weeks) 8 times spread across 3 and 9 months of age. An event-related grasping paradigm was used in which toys were presented at the midline to elicit bilateral grasping and exploration. *f*NIRS data were acquired with an NIRx NSP2 system using 8×8 blunt-tipped optodes positioned over the primary sensorimotor cortex. In continuous recording, grasping trials lasted ~15 s with ~10 s rest. Custom, infant-adapted code for NIRS toolbox was used for processing by performing a subject-level GLM (AR-IRLS), and a mixed-effect model to assess longitudinal effects on HbO.

Results: Preterm infants (mean gestational age: 30 weeks) showed lower overall HbO responses compared to both performance-matched peers ($p = .008$; $d = -0.28$) and age-matched peers ($p = .160$; $d = -0.18$). At channel level, age-matched peers showed medium to high effect sizes for HbO. In performance-matched comparison, effect sizes ranged from very low to high for HbO in the right hemisphere and from low to high for HbO in the left hemisphere. Channel-wise differences only reached uncorrected significance in the right hemisphere for both age-matched ($p < .010$) and performance-matched ($p < .050$) peers.

Conclusion: Preterm infants exhibit reduced neural activation, particularly in the right hemisphere, during early goal-directed upper limb movements compared to both their age-matched and performance-matched peers. These results highlight the impact of prematurity on neural development especially when observed motor performance appears similar.

Keywords: early movement maturation, upper limb, preterm, brain maturation, infants

How many trials are enough? An *f*NIRS study of real and illusory movement

10 June
1:30pm
SF1

Brieuc Léger^{1,2*}, Ophélie Pila^{3*}, Christophe Duret³, Arthus Peltais⁴,
Julien Bonnal^{1,5}, and Stéphane Perrey²

¹Centre Hospitalier Universitaire d'Orléans, Service de Neurologie et Unité
Neurovasculaire, 14 Avenue de l'Hôpital, 45067 Orléans Cedex 2, France

²EuroMov Digital Health in Motion, Univ Montpellier, IMT Mines Alès, Montpellier,
France

³Centre de Rééducation Fonctionnelle Les Trois Soleils, Unité de Neurorééducation,
Boissise-Le-Roi, France

⁴Centre Hospitalier Universitaire d'Orléans, Département de recherche clinique, 14 Avenue
de l'Hôpital, 45067 Orléans Cedex 2, France

⁵Université d'Orléans, SAPRéM, Orléans, France

Background and Objective: In movement science, there are no recommendations regarding the number of trials (NoT) required to stabilize the intertrial variability of the cerebral hemodynamic response (CHR) in *f*NIRS block design. This study aimed to determine the minimum NoT required to stabilize CHR variability, based on $\Delta[\text{HbO}]$ and $\Delta[\text{HbR}]$ measured by *f*NIRS during a motor and a proprioceptive task.

Methods: Twenty-six young, healthy, right-handed individuals (24 ± 5 years, 13 females) performed a volitional opening/closing right-hand task (1-Hz metronome) and experienced vibration-induced illusory (80 Hz) arm flexion. Trials lasted 10-second with a [12-20]-second intertrial interval, and were presented 20 times. The order was counterbalanced. Continuous-wave *f*NIRS measurements (25 Hz) were localized on bi-hemispheric sensorimotor and frontoparietal areas. Bad channels were pruned (visually/QT-NIRS). Data were corrected (NIRSTORM) for movements, frequencies and superficial noise. Based on cumulative moving average over trials ($\Delta[\text{HbO}]$, $\Delta[\text{HbR}]$), task ([5-15] seconds) standard deviations were extracted. The response was estimated with a Generalized Additive Model. Finally, splines ($< .010$) detected the plateau, resulting in the minimum NoT.

Results: In the volitional condition, minimum NoT for the contralateral sensorimotor area was 9/13 (HbO/HbR). In the illusory condition, the minimal NoT for the contralateral sensorimotor area was 5/5, and 9/10 for the frontoparietal areas.

Conclusion: The results indicate that the signal appears to stabilize at a different NoT for voluntary and illusory movements, depending on the areas and chromophores. This finding should be considered in *f*NIRS studies to ensure detecting CHR, and limiting fatigability/habituation. This paves the way for future standardization of *f*NIRS movement science block design studies.

Keywords: *f*NIRS, trials, block design, movement, illusion

10 June
2:00pm
SF1

Development and evaluation of a multimodal EEG-*f*NIRS neurofeedback platform for motor imagery

Camille Muller^{1,2*}, Isabelle Corouge², Thomas Prampart³, Elise Bannier^{2,4},
and Pierre Maurel²

¹CerCo, Centre de Recherche Cerveau et Cognition, Université de Toulouse, CNRS, UPS, Toulouse, France

²Univ Rennes, Inria, CNRS, Inserm, Empenn ERL U1228, Rennes, France

³Univ Rennes, Inria, CNRS, IRISA, Rennes, France

⁴CHU Rennes, Department of Radiology, Rennes, France

Background and Objective: Neurofeedback (NF) promotes neuroplasticity by enabling users to self-regulate brain activity. NF based on motor imagery (MI) specifically focuses on motor targets in the brain to stimulate brain plasticity. Recently the combination of several neuroimaging methods to characterize brain activity has led to growing interest. While NF traditionally relies on electroencephalography (EEG), integrating functional near-infrared spectroscopy (*f*NIRS) could offer a more comprehensive characterization of task-related activity by combining electrical and hemodynamic information. This study assesses a multimodal EEG-*f*NIRS based NF platform for upper-limb MI, a combination still under-explored.

Methods: We developed a custom platform for real-time signal processing, synchronization, and *f*NIRS physiological noise mitigation to provide NF scores and visual feedback. Thirty participants (15 women, 25 ± 4 years) performed three randomized MI-NF sessions: EEG-only, *f*NIRS-only, and multimodal based NF. The NF score, derived from right primary motor cortex activity during left-hand MI, was displayed via a visual gauge. Methodological focus included joint recording constraints and online signal quality.

Results: Participants successfully achieved NF control in all conditions. However, no significant differences were observed between unimodal and multimodal sessions regarding displayed scores. Furthermore, neurophysiological analysis revealed no significant difference in brain activity within the right primary motor cortex for either EEG or *f*NIRS signals across conditions.

Conclusion: While demonstrating the feasibility of a robust, real-time multimodal NF system, the EEG-*f*NIRS combination provided no specific advantage under this protocol. Future work will explore other brain regions and investigate the long-term effects of multimodal training on motor learning and post-stroke rehabilitation optimization.

Keywords: *f*NIRS-EEG integration, multimodal neurofeedback, motor imagery, real-time processing, BCI

Poster Session

Vasoreactivity of the prefrontal cortex during exercise in men living with type 1 diabetes following a single dose of cocoa flavanols

Elodie Lespagnol^{1*}, Costantino Balestra², Julie Dereumetz¹, Cassandra Parent¹, Julien Boissière¹, Sémah Tagougui¹, Clément Leveque², Michel P. Hermans³, Martin Feelisch⁴, Patrice Maboudou⁵, Farid Zerimech⁵, Romain Meeusen⁶, Cajsa Tonoli⁶, Danusa D. Soares⁷, and Elsa Heyman^{1,8}

¹Univ. Lille, Univ. Artois, Univ. Littoral Côte d'Opale, ULR 7369 - URePSSS - Unité de Recherche Pluridisciplinaire Sport Santé Société, F-59000 Lille, France

²Environmental, Occupational, Ageing (Integrative) Physiology Laboratory, HE2b, Bruxelles, Belgique

³Department of Endocrinology and Nutrition, Cliniques Universitaires Saint-Luc, Avenue Hippocrate, 10, 1200, Brussels, Belgium

⁴Experimental Medicine & Integrative Biology, University of Southampton, Faculty of Medicine, Southampton, England

⁵CHU de Lille, Laboratoire de Biochimie et Biologie Moléculaire, Pôle de Biologie Pathologie Génétique, Lille, France

⁶Human Physiology research group, Faculty of Physical Education and Physical Therapy, Vrije Universiteit Brussels, Belgium

⁶Laboratório de Fisiologia do Exercício - LAFISE - Escola de Educação Física, Fisioterapia e Terapia Ocupacional EEFETO-UFMG, Belo Horizonte, Brasil

⁸Institut Universitaire de France (IUF)

Background and Objective: People living with type 1 diabetes (T1D) may exhibit impaired prefrontal cortex vasoreactivity in response to intense aerobic exercise. This may be linked to early endothelial dysfunction and the associated reduction in nitric oxide (NO•) bioavailability. It appears essential to identify and test non-pharmacological interventions to improve exercise-induced vasoreactivity in these patients. Among the bioactive components of food, cocoa flavanols are currently attracting attention: in particular, they may increase NO• production or prevent its inactivation.

Methods: Twelve men with T1D and no vascular complications, as well as twelve men without diabetes (matched for BMI, age and physical activity level), took part in three visits in a randomised (double-blind) order to test the effect of an acute dose (+2 hours) of a cocoa bean extract rich in flavanols (900 mg) versus a

placebo containing only maltodextrin and another placebo containing theobromine and caffeine in quantities equivalent to those in the cocoa bean extract. Participants performed a maximal incremental exercise test during which vascular reactivity and oxygenation of the prefrontal cortex were measured using near-infrared spectroscopy. Blood samples taken before and after exercise were analysed to measure parameters related to NO• metabolism and oxidative stress.

Results: Flavanols do not appear to have any effect on blood parameters at rest. During exercise, compared with the placebo containing only maltodextrin, the placebo containing theobromine and caffeine, as well as the ‘Flavanols’ condition, appear to improve cerebral vasoreactivity whilst increasing plasma uric acid (an antioxidant) but also, surprisingly, increasing endocan (a marker of endothelial dysfunction). The effect of the flavanols did not differ between participants with T1D and non-diabetic controls.

Conclusion: It would appear that the vasoactive compounds contained in the flavanol-rich extract derived from cocoa are theobromine and caffeine rather than the flavanols themselves. This remains to be confirmed by further blood tests (for nitrites, etc.), which are currently being analysed.

Keywords: type 1 diabetes, vasoreactivity, flavanols, NO metabolism, exercise

User acceptability and ergonomic evaluation of a portable *f*NIRS avatar during ecological motor activities

Valentin Cretaine^{1*}, Alice Martinez^{1*}, Morgane Pinot^{1*}, Ségolène M. R. Guérin³,
and Jean-Dominique Guérin^{1,2}

¹Pôle S-mart Hauts-de-France, UPHF, F-59313 Valenciennes, France

²INSA Hauts-de-France, UMR 8201 - LAMIH - Laboratoire d'Automatique, de Mécanique
et d'Informatique industrielles et Humaines, F-59313 Valenciennes, France

³Univ. Littoral Côte d'Opale, Univ. Artois, Univ. Lille, ULR 7369 - URePSSS - Unité de
Recherche Pluridisciplinaire Sport Santé Société, F-59140 Dunkerque, France

Background and Objective: *f*NIRS is a neuroimaging technique particularly well suited to the investigation of brain activity in naturalistic environments and during ecological motor tasks. The growing availability of wireless *f*NIRS systems has facilitated the acquisition of neurophysiological data during whole-body movements. However, the practical feasibility of wireless *f*NIRS recordings during complex motor activities, as well as user acceptance and ergonomic considerations associated with such devices, remain insufficiently explored. The objective of this study is to design an avatar of an existing portable *f*NIRS device and to evaluate its acceptability and usability in healthy adult participants.

Methods: A portable wireless *f*NIRS avatar based on the MedelOpt Mobility system (Seenel Imaging) was designed following an iterative development process combining literature review, ergonomic analysis, computer-aided design, and rapid prototyping techniques, including 3D printing. Functional specifications were defined to optimise portability, comfort, and stability during whole-body movement. Feasibility and acceptability testing is currently being conducted in healthy adults during three types of motor activity: basketball, Nordic walking and table tennis. Quantitative and qualitative measures are being collected to assess usability, comfort and perceived burden during movement.

Results: The avatar is expected to demonstrate satisfactory ergonomic properties and a high level of user acceptance during movement-based tasks.

Conclusion: Beyond improving the feasibility and implementation of ecological neuroimaging paradigms, the outcomes of this project may contribute to the development of portable neuroimaging solutions for clinical applications, particularly in the field of physical rehabilitation for stroke survivors.

Keywords: avatar, acceptability, ergonomics, conception, user experience

Exploring the effects of body position on neurobiological, behavioral and psychophysiological dynamics

Paul Butin^{1*}, Layan Fessler¹, and Cédric T. Bonnet¹

¹Univ. Lille, CNRS, UMR 9193 - SCALab - Sciences Cognitives et Sciences Affectives, F-59000 Lille, France

Background and Objective: Modern professional life is increasingly defined by sedentary office environments, where prolonged sitting is associated with chronic diseases and cognitive deficits. While sit-stand desks are popular solutions to encourage alternating between body position, the neurobiological and physiological consequences of body position (sitting vs. standing) on task performance remain insufficiently explored.

Methods: Two studies will adopt an integrative approach to investigate the relationship between body position and cognitive performance in young adults. Participants will perform attentional tasks, like Posner task and a Psychomotor Vigilance Task (PVT) in both sitting and standing positions. Multi-modal data collection includes hemodynamic responses in the prefrontal cortex via *f*NIRS, autonomic activity (heart rate, respiration, electrodermal activity), and behavioral measures such as reaction time. Study 1 will investigate how psychological factors modulate the relationship between attention and body position by examining affective responses like anticipated pleasure. In contrast, Study 2 will focus on physical aspects, incorporating exploratory analyses of the center of pressure (COP) to assess the impact of body sway on vigilance. These complementary approaches will provide a better framework for assessing attentional performance across different body positions.

Results: We hypothesize that the standing position will predict higher task performance, increased prefrontal cortex oxygenated hemoglobin (HbO₂), and elevated heart rate compared to sitting.

Conclusion: These findings are expected to advance the theoretical understanding of how body position influences the interaction between cognitive, neurobiological responses.

Keywords: body position, task performance, *f*NIRS, psychophysiological activity, prefrontal activity

Cortical activation during robot-based sensory processing in stroke and healthy controls: A pilot *f*NIRS study

Siqi Yang^{1*}, Charlotte Heremans¹, Inês Martins², Jolien Gooijers^{2,3},
Jean-Jacques Orban de Xivry^{2,3}, and Geert Verheyden^{1,3}

¹Department of Rehabilitation Sciences, KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium

²Department of Movement Sciences, KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium

³Leuven Brain Institute, KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium

Background and Objective: Stroke often leads to persistent upper limb impairments, and altered sensory processing has been suggested to contribute to sensorimotor dysfunction, but its neural basis remains unclear. This pilot study aimed to evaluate the feasibility of using *f*NIRS to assess cortical activation during a robot-based sensory processing task in patients with chronic stroke, with exploratory comparisons to age-matched healthy controls.

Methods: Three patients with chronic stroke and three age-matched healthy controls participated in the pilot study. Cortical activity was recorded using a wireless NIRSport2 system. Optodes covered prefrontal and sensorimotor regions, including DLPFC, PMC/SMA, M1, S1, and the somatosensory association cortex (SAC). Participants performed an in-house developed sensory processing paradigm using the Kinarm robot in a block design. Participants used their affected or non-dominant arm to trace a virtual kite-shaped contour without visual feedback and judged which side was longer after completion of the trial.

Results: During the sensory processing paradigm, stroke participants descriptively showed higher ΔHbO responses than healthy controls across several cortical regions, particularly in bilateral SAC and ipsilesional S1/M1. Task performance was high in both groups, with near-ceiling accuracy (all participants ≥ 0.9).

Conclusion: This pilot study demonstrates the feasibility of using *f*NIRS to detect stroke-related cortical alterations during robot-based sensory processing tasks. Increased activation in key sensorimotor regions in stroke participants may reflect compensatory cortical recruitment. These results support the use of *f*NIRS to investigate the neural mechanisms of sensorimotor rehabilitation and provide a basis for future longitudinal studies.

Keywords: stroke patients, neuroplasticity, sensorimotor rehabilitation, upper limb function, robot therapy

Multimodal *f*NIRS-EEG recording during standing cognitive tasks in an immersive olfactory dome

Marine R. Coeugnet^{1*}, Zeynep Yenigun¹, Thomas Fontaine²,
Yvonne N. Delevoye-Turrell^{1,3}, and Marion A. Vincent²

¹Univ. Lille, CNRS, UMR 9193 - SCALab - Sciences Cognitives et Sciences Affectives,
F-59000 Lille, France

²SEENEL Imaging, Tourcoing, France

³Institut Universitaire de France (IUF)

Background and Objective: Olfactory environments are increasingly used to support cognitive engagement in everyday settings, yet their neurophysiological correlates remain poorly documented, especially in ecological contexts where participants are standing. Synchronized *f*NIRS and EEG recordings capture complementary hemodynamic and electrophysiological dynamics. Such multimodal approaches are essential to uncover the underlying mechanisms of cognitive engagement. However, their deployment in immersive contexts raises significant methodological challenges. This exploratory study assessed the feasibility of multimodal *f*NIRS-EEG recordings during standing cognitive tasks within a novel olfactory dome, while examining how candle-based environments shape sustained attention and creativity.

Methods: Thirteen healthy adults performed a Sustained Attention to Response Task (SART; spacebar presses) and an Alternative Uses Task (AUT; typing on a laptop) while standing inside an olfactory dome. Six candle conditions were tested (three scents: floral, green, neutral; two lighting: lit, unlit). Frontal *f*NIRS and EEG were recorded simultaneously, with cardiac and respiratory signals monitored to account for physiological artifacts. Subjective cognitive load was assessed using the NASA-TLX.

Results: While NASA-TLX scores indicated no subjective difference across conditions, *f*NIRS revealed a significant odor effect on frontal HbO during the final minutes of cognitive engagement ($\chi_2(2) = 11.743$, $p = .038$), converging with EEG modulations of frontal alpha power ($\chi_2(2) = 7.6$, $p = .022$). Behaviorally, the floral scent enhanced creative elaboration ($p = .018$).

Conclusion: This study demonstrates the feasibility of synchronized *f*NIRS-EEG recordings during standing cognitive tasks in immersive olfactory environments, revealing convergent hemodynamic and oscillatory signatures of scent-dependent frontal engagement. These findings open avenues for ecological neuroimaging in sensory environments.

Keywords: *f*NIRS-EEG, olfactory dome, scented candles, sustained attention, creativity

Improving *f*NIRS neuroimaging data analysis during motor paradigms by integrating systemic physiological signals

Salomé L. Delbecq^{1*}, Pierre Morel¹, Hadi Abou Nader², and Ségolène M. R. Guérin¹

¹Univ. Littoral Côte d’Opale, Univ. Artois, Univ. Lille, ULR 7369 - URePSSS - Unité de Recherche Pluridisciplinaire Sport Santé Société, F-59140 Dunkerque, France

²Université Paris Cité, France

Background and Objective: *f*NIRS is particularly well suited for investigating brain activity during motor production. However, *f*NIRS signals are sensitive to non-neuronal systemic physiological fluctuations, such as heart rate and partial pressure of CO₂. These fluctuations can lead to misinterpretation of cortical activation, especially during tasks associated with substantial physiological load. Systemic physiology-augmented *f*NIRS (SPA-*f*NIRS) enables the simultaneous acquisition of these physiological signals, allowing for improved isolation of the neuronal components. However, the use of SPA-*f*NIRS during motor tasks is underdeveloped. The primary aim of this study is to identify which physiological signals contribute the most to *f*NIRS data contamination, in order to inform methodological recommendations. A secondary aim is to develop a semi-automated preprocessing pipeline for *f*NIRS data that incorporates removal of non-neuronal physiological signals.

Methods: Healthy adults aged 18–45 years will take part in a single experimental session. Prefrontal, motor and occipital brain activity will be recorded using *f*NIRS alongside physiological measures (e.g., gas exchange, heart rate, blood pressure) during three motor tasks: finger tapping, low-intensity cycling and moderate-intensity cycling. Each task will be performed at three different paces (400, 600 and 1300 ms) to modulate physiological load.

Results: We hypothesize that preprocessing based on physiological regression will reduce spurious activations unrelated to neuronal activity.

Conclusion: This study will highlight the value of SPA-*f*NIRS in motor neuroscience and sport science, with the aim of improving measurement reliability. It will also contribute to ongoing efforts towards the standardization of *f*NIRS data analysis.

Keywords: SPA-*f*NIRS, motor tasks, physiological measurements, data processing, motion artifacts

Effects of movement tempo on prefrontal cortical activation during short-term sensorimotor synchronization practice

Hadi Abou Nader^{1,2*}, Pierre Morel², Salomé L. Delbecq²,
and Ségolène M. R. Guérin²

¹Université Paris Cité, France

²Univ. Littoral Côte d'Opale, Univ. Artois, Univ. Lille, ULR 7369 - URePSSS - Unité de Recherche Pluridisciplinaire Sport Santé Société, F-59140 Dunkerque, France

Background and Objective: Movement is fundamental to human activity and represents the primary means by which individuals interact with their environment. To stay coordinated with external demands, humans must constantly adjust movement timing. Previous research has shown that cognitive load and prefrontal activity increase as movement speed decreases. However, it remains unclear how short-term practice modulates the cognitive, inhibitory control required to slow movement pace. The objective of this study is to examine how short-term practice influences prefrontal cortical activation during sensorimotor synchronization at different paces.

Methods: Thirty participants will perform a sensorimotor-synchronization task at three paces (fast, close-to-spontaneous and slow). To examine generalizability of the findings, three tasks will be performed: finger tapping, low- and moderate- intensity cycling. The brain responses of participants over the prefrontal will be recorded throughout using *f*NIRS. For each experimental condition, 6 trials of 40 sec will be performed. Data will be preprocessed using a SPA-*f*NIRS approach to reduce the systemic physiological noise associated with body movements.

Results: We hypothesize that more prefrontal activity will be observed in slow trials, regardless of the task. In addition, a progressive decrease in prefrontal activity should be observed over repetitions only in the slow condition.

Conclusion: If verified, these findings would indicate that movement speed modulates prefrontal activity, with slower tempi requiring greater cognitive effort. A progressive reduction in prefrontal activation across repeated slow-tempo trials would suggest decreased reliance on executive control with practice, reflecting increased automatization associated with motor learning. These results would highlight movement speed as a critical parameter for optimizing both athletic training and clinical rehabilitation.

Keywords: SPA-*f*NIRS, motor learning, motor timing, neurophysiology, prefrontal cortex

Keywords Index

acceptability, 17
affect, 7
aging, 10
automatic process, 5
avatar, 17

BCI, 14
bicycle riding, 5
block design, 13
body position, 18
brain maturation, 11, 12

cerebral oximetry, 6, 7
conception, 17
cortical activity, 10
creativity, 20

data processing, 21

early movement maturation, 11, 12
effort, 7
ergonomics, 17
exercise, 10, 16

flavanols, 16
*f*NIRS-EEG, 14, 20

illusion, 13
infants, 11, 12

motion artifacts, 21
motor imagery, 14
motor learning, 22
motor tasks, 21
motor timing, 22
movement, 13
movement artifact, 5
multimodal neurofeedback, 14
multimodal sensing, 9

neurophysiology, 22
neuroplasticity, 19
NO metabolism, 16

olfactory dome, 20

Parkinson's Disease, 10
physical activity, 6, 7
physiological measurements, 21
physiological noise, 9
prefrontal cortex, 5, 6, 18, 22
preterm, 12
psychophysiological activity, 18

real-time processing, 14
robot therapy, 19

scented candles, 20
sensorimotor rehabilitation, 19
short-separation regression, 9
SPA-*f*NIRS, 21, 22
stationary bike, 5, 6
stroke patients, 19
sustained attention, 20

task performance, 18
trials, 13
type 1 diabetes, 16
typical developing, 11

upper limb, 11, 12, 19
user experience, 17

vasoreactivity, 16
ventilatory threshold, 6

walking, 10
wearable neurotechnology, 9

Author Index

- Abou Nader
Hadi, 21, 22
- Balestra
Costantino, 15
- Bannier
Elise, 14
- Bherer
Louis, 8
- Bigliassi
Marcelo, 6
- Boissière
Julien, 15
- Bonnal
Julien, 13
- Bonnet
Cédrick T., 18
- Butin
Paul, 18
- Bégel
Valentin, 8
- Cheminon
Maxime, 10
- Coeugnet
Marine R., 6, 20
- Corouge
Isabelle, 14
- Cretaine
Valentin, 17
- Danaila
Teodor, 10
- De Beukelaer
Nathalie, 11, 12
- De Bruyn
Nele, 11, 12
- Delbecq
Salomé L., 21, 22
- Delevoye-Turrell
Yvonne N., 6, 7, 20
- Dereumetz
Julie, 15
- Derollepot
Romain, 10
- Dubuis
Laura, 5
- Duret
Christophe, 13
- Feelisch
Martin, 15
- Fessler
Layan, 7, 18
- Fontaine
Thomas, 20
- Gooijers
Jolien, 19
- Guérin
Jean-Dominique, 17
Ségolène M. R., 6, 7, 17, 21, 22
- Heremans
Charlotte, 19
- Hermans
Michel P., 15
- Heyman
Elsa, 15
- Hoang
Isabelle, 10
- Karageorghis
Costas I., 6

Khan
 Khadija, 9
 Lambert Cause
 Joan, 9
 Lamers
 Jolien, 11, 12
 Lespagnol
 Elodie, 15
 Leveque
 Clément, 15
 Luauté
 Jacques, 10
 Léger
 Brieuc, 13
 Maboudou
 Patrice, 15
 Martinez
 Alice, 17
 Martins
 Inês, 19
 Maurel
 Pierre, 14
 May
 François, 5
 Meeusen
 Romain, 15
 Morel
 Pierre, 21, 22
 Muller
 Antoine, 5
 Camille, 14
 Orban de Xivry
 Jean-Jacques, 19
 Paire-Ficout
 Laurence, 10
 Parent
 Cassandra, 15
 Peltais
 Arthus, 13
 Perrey
 Stéphane, 13
 Pila
 Ophélie, 13
 Pinot
 Morgane, 17
 Place
 Ugo, 8
 Pollonini
 Luca, 2
 Prampart
 Thomas, 14
 Ranchet
 Maud, 5, 10
 Robert
 Thomas, 5
 Soares
 Danusa D., 15
 Stiens
 Johan, 9
 Tagougui
 Sémah, 15
 Tonoli
 Cajsa, 15
 Van den Berghe
 Pieter, 11, 12
 Van den Broeck
 Broeck, 11, 12
 Verheyden
 Geert, 19
 Vincent
 Marion A., 20
 Thomas, 8
 Vitiello
 Damien, 8
 Yang
 Siqi, 19
 Yenigun
 Zeynep, 20
 Yücel
 Meryem, 1
 Zaoui
 Yanis, 8
 Zerimech
 Farid, 15

*f*AME

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